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Content Based Image Retrieval Using Color And Texture

Manimala Singha and K. Hemachandran, Assam University, India

ABSTRACT

The increased need of content based image retrieval technique can be found in a number of different domains such as Data Mining, Education, Medical Imaging, Crime Prevention, Weather forecasting, Remote Sensing and Management of Earth Resources. This paper presents the content based image retrieval, using features like texture and color, called WBCHIR (Wavelet Based Color Histogram Image Retrieval). The texture and color features are extracted through wavelet transformation and color histogram and the combination of these features is robust to scaling and translation of objects in an image. The proposed system has demonstrated a promising and faster retrieval method on a WANG image database containing 1000 general-purpose color images. The performance has been evaluated by comparing with the existing systems in the literature.

KEYWORDS

Image Retrieval, Color Histogram, Color Spaces, Quantization, Similarity Matching, Haar Wavelet, Precision and Recall.

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AUTHORS

Ms. Manimala Singha received her B.Sc. and M.Sc. degrees in Computer Science from Assam University, Silchar in 2005 and 2007 respectively. Presently she is working, for her Ph.D., as a Research Scholar and her area of interest includes image segmentation, feature extraction, and image searching in large databases

Prof. K. Hemachandran is associated with the Dept. of Computer Science, Assam University, Silchar, since 1998. He obtained his M.Sc. Degree from Sri Venkateswara University, Tirupati and M.Tech. and Ph.D. Degrees from Indian School of Mines, Dhanbad. His areas of research interest are Image Processing, Software Engineering and Distributed Computing.

Rain Streaks Elimination Using Image Processing Algorithms

Dinesh Kadam¹, Amol R. Madane², Krishnan Kutty² and S. V. Bonde¹, ¹SGGSIET, India and
²Tata Consultancy Services Ltd., India

ABSTRACT

The paper addresses the problem of rain streak removal from videos. While, Rain streak removal from scene is important but a lot of research in this area, robust and real time algorithms is unavailable in the market. Difficulties in the rain streak removal algorithm arises due to less visibility, less illumination, and availability of moving camera and objects. The challenge that plagues rain streak recovery algorithm is detecting rain streaks and replacing them with original values to recover the scene. In this paper, we discuss the use of photometric and chromatic properties for rain detection. Updated Gaussian Mixture Model (Updated GMM) has detected moving objects. This rain streak removal algorithm is used to detect rain streaks from videos and replace it with estimated values, which is equivalent to original value. The spatial and temporal properties are used to replace rain streaks with its original values.

KEYWORDS

Dynamic Scene, Edge Filters, Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM), Rain Streaks Removal, Scene Recovery, Video Deraining

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Application of A Computer Vision Method for Soiling Recognition in Photovoltaic Modules for Autonomous Cleaning Robots

Tatiani Pivem¹, Felipe de Oliveira de Araujo², Laura de Oliveira de Araujo², Gustavo Spontoni de Oliveira², ¹Federal University of Mato Grosso do Sul - UFMS, Brazil and ²Nexsolar Energy Solutions, Brazil

ABSTRACT

It is well known that this soiling can reduce the generation efficiency in PV system. In some case according to the literature of loss of energy production in photovoltaic systems can reach up to 50%. In the industry there are various types of cleaning robots, they can substitute the human action, reducing cleaning cost, be used in places where access is difficult, and increasing significantly the gain of the systems. In this paper we present an application of computer vision method for soiling recognition in photovoltaic modules for autonomous cleaning robots. Our method extends classic CV algorithm such Region Growing and the Hough. Additionally, we adopt a pre-processing technique based on Top Hat and Edge detection filters. We have performed a set of experiments to test and validate this method. The article concludes that the developed method can bring more intelligence to photovoltaic cleaning robots.

KEYWORDS

Solar Panel, Soiling Identification, Cartesian Robots, Autonomous Robots, Computer Vision

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AUTHORS

Tatiani Pivem – was born in Assis-SP, on September 27, 1991. She has a degree in Electrical Engineering – USP 2015, Tatiani has experience in Research and Development, was CPqD intern in 2014, now she is at the master in Energy Efficiency and Sustainability at UFMS and works with Software Coordinator research and development at Nexsolar

Felipe de Oliveira de Araujo – was born in Campo Grande, MS, Brazil on July 11, 1991. He has a degree in Electrical Engineering – UFMS. He has master in Energetic Efficiency and Sustainability. Worked in Spain and now he is CEO at Nexsolar. Your main goal is to make energy accessible for everyone. Felipe works as Director of R&D programs.

Laura de Oliveira de Araujo – was born in Campo Grande, MS, Brazil on July 11, 1991. Ambiental Engineer – UFMS 2015. Laura has specialization at Work Security UFMS 2018. Laura works in solar energy area, she is CFO at Nexsolar, your main goal is to make energy accessible for everyone. Laura has specialization at Work Security UFMS 2018. Laura works in solar energy area, she is CFO at Nexsolar, your main goal is to make energy accessible for everyone.

Gustavo Spontoni de Oliveira – was born in Campo Grande, MS, Brazil on March 03, 1995. He is currently a designer and researcher at Nexsolar. Civil Engineer, graduated from Anhanguera University - UNIDERP. Experience in structural masonry, concrete block manufacturing, photovoltaic systems and energy efficiency projects.

Machine-Learning Estimation of Body Posture and Physical Activity by Wearable Acceleration and Heartbeat Sensors

Yutaka Yoshida², Emi Yuda^{3, 1}, Kento Yamamoto⁴, Yutaka Miura⁵ and Junichiro Hayano¹, ¹Nagoya City University Graduate School of Medical Science, Japan, ²Nagoya City University Graduate School of Design and Architecture, Japan, ³Tohoku University Graduate School of Engineering, Japan, ⁴University of Tsukuba Graduate School of Comprehensive Human Sciences, Japan and ⁵Shigakkan University, Japan

ABSTRACT

We aimed to develop the method for estimating body posture and physical activity by acceleration signals from a Holter electrocardiographic (ECG) recorder with built-in accelerometer. In healthy young subjects, triaxial-acceleration and ECG signal were recorded with the Holter ECG recorder attached on their chest wall. During the recording, they randomly took eight postures, including supine, prone, left and right recumbent, standing, sitting in a reclining chair, sitting in chairs with and without backrest, and performed slow walking and fast walking. Machine learning (Random Forest) was performed on acceleration and ECG variables. The best discrimination model was obtained when the maximum values and standard deviations of accelerations in three axes and mean R-R interval were used as feature values. The overall discrimination accuracy was 79.2% (62.6-90.9%). Supine, prone, left recumbent, and slow and fast walk were discriminated with >80% accuracy, although sitting and standing positions were not discriminated by this method.

KEYWORDS

Accelerometer, Holter ECG, Posture, Activity, Machine learning, Random Forest, R-R interval

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AUTHORS

Yutaka Yoshida studied the business administration and computer science at Aichi Institute of Technology and received Ph.D. degree in 2008. He was a project researcher at Knowledge Hub of Aichi from 2011 to 2015 and was a researcher at Nagoya City University Graduate School of Medical Sciences from 2016 to 2017. Since 2018, he has been a researcher at Nagoya City University Graduate School of Design and Architecture. His specialized field is biological information engineering, signal processing and ergonomics. He received the paper award at the Japan Society of Neurovegetative Research in 2005 and 2007.

Emi Yuda was born in Tokyo, Japan in 1980. She studied informatics at M.V.Lomonosov Moscow State University until 2003 and then received M.S. degree from Tsukuba University, Japan. She received Ph.D. from Nihon University in 2019. From 2013 to 2014 she was a research assistant at Santa Monica College in California, USA. From 2015 to 2019, she was a NEDO project researcher in Nagoya City University Graduate School of Medical Sciences. Since 2019, she has been an assistant professor in Tohoku University Graduate School of Engineering. Her currently research is Medical Informatics and Data Science. She has many achievements in field of Informatics and Big Data.

Junichiro Hayano graduated Nagoya City University Medical School, Nagoya, Japan and received M.D. degree in 1980. From 1981 to 1983, he received residency trainings of psychosomatic medicine in Kyushu University School of Medicine, Fukuoka, Japan. He obtained Ph.D. degree (Dr. of Medical Science) in 1988 from Nagoya City University Graduate School of Medical Sciences. From 1990 to 1991, he was working as a visiting associate at the Behavioral Medicine Research Center, Duke University Medical Center, Durham, NC, USA. In 1984, he got a faculty position at Nagoya City University Medical School and has been a Professor of Medicine at Nagoya City University Graduate School of Medical Sciences since 2003. His current interests are applications of dynamic electrocardiography and bio-signal processing to health sciences.

RGBEXCEL : An RGB Image Data Extractor and Exporter for Excel Processing

Peter A. Larbi^{1,2}, ¹Arkansas State University, USA and ²University of Arkansas, USA

ABSTRACT

The objective of this paper was to develop a means of rapidly obtaining RGB image data, as part of an effort to develop a low-cost method of image processing and analysis based on Microsoft Excel. A simple standalone GUI (graphical user interface) software application called RGB Excel was developed to extract RGB image data from any colour image files of any format. For a given image file, the output from the software is an Excel file with the data from the R (red), G (green), and B (blue) bands of the image contained in different sheets. The raw data and any enhancements can be visualized by using the surface chart type in combination with other features. Since Excel can plot a maximum dimension of 255 by 255 pixels, larger images are downscaled to have a maximum dimension of 255 pixels. Results from testing the application are discussed in the paper.

KEYWORDS

RGB image, Image processing, Microsoft Excel, Software Development, MATLAB

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AUTHOR

Dr. Peter Ako Larbi joined the College of Agriculture and Technology, Arkansas State University, in August 2014 as an assistant professor of Agricultural Systems Technology, with a joint appointment with the Division of Agriculture, University of Arkansas. Prior to this, he had about three-and-a-half years of postdoctoral research experiences from University of Florida’s Citrus Research and Education Center in Lake Alfred, FL and Washington State University’s Center for Precision and Automated Agricultural Systems in Prosser, WA. He has a bachelor’s and a master’s degrees in Agricultural Engineering from the Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology in Ghana and a Ph.D. in Agricultural and Biological Engineering from the University of Florida. His teaching interests include Modern Agricultural Systems, Remote Sensing, Modern Irrigation Systems, and Precision Application Technology. His research interests include precision agriculture technologies, remote sensing, and agricultural machinery automation.

Colour-Texture Image Segmentation Using Hypercomplex Gabor Analysis

B. D. Venkatramana Reddy¹ and T. Jayachandra Prasad¹, ¹Madanapalle Institute of Technology & Science, India and ²RGM College of Engineering & Technology, India

ABSTRACT

Texture analysis such as segmentation and classification plays a vital role in computer vision and pattern recognition and is widely applied to many areas such as industrial automation, bio-medical image processing and remote sensing. In this paper, we first extend the well-known Gabor filters to color images using a specific form of hypercomplex numbers known as quaternions. These filters are constructed as windowed basis functions of the quaternion Fourier transform also known as hypercomplex Fourier transform. Based on this extension this paper presents the use of these new quaternionic Gabor filters in colour texture image segmentation. Experimental results on two colour texture images are presented. We tested the robustness of this technique for segmentation by adding Gaussian noise to the texture images. Experimental results indicate that the proposed method gives better segmentation results even in the presence of strongest noise.

KEYWORDS

Colour texture image segmentation, Gabor filters, hypercomplex numbers, quaternions, quaternion Fourier transform.

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AUTHORS

B.D.Venkatramana Reddy is currently working as professor in ECE Department, Madanapalle Institute of Technology&Science, Madanapalle, India. He received his M.Tech from S.V.University, Tirupathi, India. He has 12 years experience of teaching undergraduate and post graduate students. He has published 12 research papers in National/International conferences and journals. His research interests are in the areas of signal processing and digital image processing.

Dr.T.Jayachandra Prasad obtained his B.Tech in Electronics and Communication Engg., from JNTU College of Engineering, Anantapur 515002, and Master of Engineering degree in Applied Electronics from Coimbatore Institute of Technology, Coimbatore. He earned his Ph.D. Degree (Complex Signal Processing) in ECE from JNTUCE, Anantapur, India. Dr.T.Jayachandra Prasad worked in KSRM College of Engineering (KSRMCE), Kadapa, India from August 1984 to May 2006 in various positions such as Assistant professor, Associate professor and Professor and HOD. He worked as Head of ECE Dept. for 9 years at KSRMCE, Kadapa. He was instrumental for the establishment of various laboratories at KSRMCE. Later he joined in RGM College of Engineering and Technology, Nandyal, Kurnool (dt), Andhra Pradesh (state), INDIA. Presently, he is the Principal of RGM College of Engineering and Technology, Nandyal. Dr.T.Jayachandra is having more than 24 years of experience and has more than 18 technical publications in International journals and National Journals. He is a life member of ISTE (India), Fellow of Institution of Engineers (Kolkata), Fellow of IETE, Member of MIEEE and life member of NAFEN. His areas of interest include Signal Processing and Image Processing.

Two New Approaches for Secured Image Steganography Using Cryptographic Techniques and Type Conversions

Sujay Narayana and Gaurav Prasad, NITK - Surathkal, India

ABSTRACT

The science of securing a data by encryption is Cryptography whereas the method of hiding secret messages in other messages is Steganography, so that the secret's very existence is concealed. The term 'Steganography' describes the method of hiding cognitive content in another medium to avoid detection by the intruders. This paper introduces two new methods wherein cryptography and steganography are combined to encrypt the data as well as to hide the encrypted data in another medium so the fact that a message being sent is concealed. One of the methods shows how to secure the image by converting it into cipher text by S-DES algorithm using a secret key and conceal this text in another image by steganographic method. Another method shows a new way of hiding an image in another image by encrypting the image directly by S-DES algorithm using a key image and the data obtained is concealed in another image. The proposed method prevents the possibilities of steganalysis also.

KEYWORDS

Steganography, Cryptography, image hiding, least-significant bit (LSB) method

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AUTHORS

Sujay Narayana received the BE degree in Electronics and Communication from KVG College of Engineering, Sullia, in 2009. He is currently with the Department of Electronics and Communication, National Institute of Technology Karnataka, Surathkal.

Gaurav Prasad received the BE degree in Information Science from P.A College of Engineering, Nadupadavu, Mangalore in 2006 and MTech degree in Information Security from NITK, Surathkal. He is currently with the Department of Information Technology, National Institute of Technology Karnataka, Surathkal.

Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR) Improvement of Atmospheric Signals Using Variable Windows

P. Jagadamba¹ and P. Satyanarayana², ¹SKIT, India and ²S. V. University, India

ABSTRACT

Windows reduce the sidelobe leakages from the spectrum when applied to finite length time domain sequence. Adjustable windows can be used to control the amplitude of sidelobes with respect to main lobe. This paper presents the effect of window parameter in Dolph-chebyshev, Kaiser, Gaussian and Tukey windows on the Signal to Noise Ratio(SNR) of radar returns and proposes an optimum value of window parameters with which data may be weighed. A comparative study is made on the improvement of SNR using these variable windows.

KEYWORDS

Dolph-chebyshev, Kaiser, Gaussian and Tukey windows, sidelobe leakages

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AUTHORS

P. Jagdamba did her B. Tech and M. Tech from S.V. University, Tirupati. Presently working for Ph. D in S.V. University. She has 10 years of teaching experience. She published 11 research papers in National and International Journals. Her present interest includes RADAR systems and signal processing.

Prof. P. Sathyanarayana did his B.E, M. Tech and Ph. D from S.V. University, Tirupati. He has more than 30 years of Teaching and Research experience. He guided 3 Ph. D and 30 M. Tech Students. He is member of several committees such as NBA, UGC, AICTE etc.. His current interests include signal processing and image processing.

Design and Implementation of Digital Filter Bank to Reduce Noise and Reconstruct the Input Signals

Kawser Ahammed, Md. Ershadullah, Md. Rakebul Islam Heru and Saiful Islam, University of Dhaka, Bangladesh

ABSTRACT

The main theme of this paper is to reduce noise from the noisy composite signal and reconstruct the input signals from the composite signal by designing FIR digital filter bank. In this work, three sinusoidal signals of different frequencies and amplitudes are combined to get composite signal and a low frequency noise signal is added with the composite signal to get noisy composite signal. Finally noisy composite signal is filtered by using FIR digital filter bank to reduce noise and reconstruct the input signals.

KEYWORDS

Digital Filter Bank, Noise, LMS Filter, LMS Algorithm, Composite Signal

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AUTHORS

Kawser Ahammed received B.Sc. degree in Applied Physics, Electronics & Communication Engineering and MS degree in Applied Physics, Electronics & Communication Engineering from University of Dhaka, Dhaka, Bangladesh, in 2011 and 2012 respectively. He has published 3 international research papers. His research interests are in the areas of Signal Processing, Image Processing and Communications. He is currently trying to pursue a Doctoral Degree in Electrical Engineering from USA.

Md. Ershadullah received B.Sc. degree in Applied Physics, Electronics & Communication Engineering from University of Dhaka, Dhaka, Bangladesh, in 2011. Now he is working as a Senior System Engineer in MAKS Renewable Energy Company Limited, Bangladesh. In previous he worked as a Design & Service Engineer in Solar Intercontinental (Solar-IC) Limited, Bangladesh.

Md. Rakebul Islam Heru received B.Sc. in Applied Physics, Electronics & Communication Engineering from University of Dhaka, Dhaka, Bangladesh, in 2011. Now he is working as an Assistant Maintenance Engineer at IT operation & Communication Department in Bangladesh Bank (Central Bank of Bangladesh).

Saiful Islam is a B.Sc. final year student of Electrical & Electronic Engineering, University of Dhaka, Dhaka, Bangladesh. His research interests are in the areas of Biomedical image processing and Signal processing. At present, he is pursuing his B.Sc. final year project work in National Institute of Nuclear Medicine and Allied Sciences, BSMMU Campus, Shahbag, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Advances in Automatic Tuberculosis Detection in Chest X-Ray Images

Wai Yan Nyein Naing and Zaw Z. Htike, IIUM, Malaysia

ABSTRACT

Tuberculosis (TB) is very dangerous and rapidly spread disease in the world. In the investigating cases for suspected tuberculosis (TB), chest radiography is not only the key techniques of diagnosis based on the medical imaging but also the diagnostic radiology. So, Computer aided diagnosis (CAD) has been popular and many researchers are interested in this research areas and different approaches have been proposed for the TB detection and lung disease classification. In this paper, the medical background history of TB disease in chest X-rays and a survey of the various approaches in TB detection and classification are presented. The literature in the related methods is surveyed papers in this research area until now 2014.

KEYWORDS

CAD, Tuberculosis, Image processing, Radiographs

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